

Conference Abstract

Towards Globally Harmonized Environmental Data: A Proof of Concept Using Ecological Drought and the GERI Framework

Krutika Deshpande[‡], Cedric J. Hagen^{§,||}, Thomas G. Bornman^{¶,#,□}, Leo Chiloane[#], Gregor Feig[#], Elisa Girola[«], Siddeswara Guru[«], Christine Laney[§], Henry W. Loescher^{§,»}, Michael Mirtl^{^,∨}, Beryl Morris[«], Paula Mabee[§], Emmanuel Salmon[!] , Michael SanClements^{§,»}, Benjamin L. Ruddell[‡], Pamela L. Sullivan[?], Melinda D. Smith[§], Werner L. Kutsch[!] , Xiubo Yu[©], Steffen Zacharias[†]

[‡] School of Informatics, Computing, and Cyber Systems, Northern Arizona University, Flagstaff, AZ, United States of America

[§] Battelle, National Ecological Observatory Network (NEON), Boulder, CO, United States of America

[|] Department of Geological Sciences, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, United States of America

[¶] Department of Biochemistry and Microbiology, Rhodes University, Makhanda, South Africa

[#] South African Environmental Observation Network (SAEON), Elwandle Coastal Node, Gqeberha, South Africa

[□] Institute for Coastal and Marine Research, Nelson Mandela University, Gqeberha, South Africa

[«] Terrestrial Ecosystem Research Network (TERN) Australia, The University of Queensland, Brisbane, QLD, Australia

[»] Institute of Alpine and Arctic Research, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO, United States of America

[^] Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (UFZ), Leipzig, Germany

[∨] Umweltbundesamt GmbH, Environment Agency Austria, Vienna, Austria

[!] ICOS ERIC Head Office, Helsinki, Finland

[?] College of Earth, Ocean, and Atmospheric Sciences, Oregon State University, Corvallis, OR, United States of America

[«] Department of Biology and Graduate Degree Program in Ecology, Colorado State University, Fort Collins, CO, United States of America

[©] Chinese Ecosystem Research Network, Chinese Academy of Sciences (CERN), Beijing, China

[†] Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung - UFZ, Leipzig, Germany

Corresponding author: Henry W. Loescher (hloescher@battelleecology.org)

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Abstract

Global environmental challenges like ecological drought demand cross-border collaboration and interoperable data. The Global Ecosystem Research Infrastructure (GERI) was founded to address this need, building relationships and establishing data

sharing practices among six of the largest ecosystem research infrastructures in the world. Data harmonization is required to standardize and ingest data products from these infrastructures into a findable, accessible, interoperable, reusable (FAIR) global dataset. Harmonized global data can improve existing global climate models and inform environmental research studies.

This poster presents a proof of concept for harmonizing ecological drought-related data products including air temperature, precipitation, soil moisture, soil temperature and soil texture starting with data from NEON (USA) and TERN (Australia). The process involved crosswalks for variable names and units, term mapping, and metadata standardization using controlled vocabularies and EML. We describe both technical and institutional challenges encountered in aligning data from diverse infrastructures, including differences in structure, granularity, and documentation. These lessons are shaping the development of scalable methods and shared practices as we expand the effort to include additional networks RIs. Looking ahead, we aim to broaden the scope of harmonization to additional ecological domains. This work will be led in part by GERI's Early Career Researcher working group and pursued in collaboration with international initiatives like DroughtNet and the International Drought Experiment. These efforts mark progress toward a globally interoperable environmental data landscape in support of science, policy, and ecosystem resilience.

Presenting author

Henry W. Loescher

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Conflicts of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.